

Guideline for collecting user experiences from workshops and training sessions

November 2023

Document elaborated by the WPs 5.1 & 5.2 of the FIN-CLARIAH consortium

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The digitization of social sciences and humanities (SSH) is still in its early stages. On top of that, available digital tools and materials aimed at supporting digital humanities (DH) and computational social sciences (CSS) research processes seem to recurrently experience challenges integrating into the ways of working of SSH scholars (Warwick, 2012; Malazita, 2022). For this reason, it is important to collect data on the **experiences of end-users** with these resources, not only to understand how they interact with them but also to gain knowledge about their needs and expectations regarding these digital tools and materials. Obtaining this information will allow to adapt and create resources that truly support the ways of working of SSH scholars when it comes to DH and CSS research, which in turn will make the digitization of SSH both more efficient and sustainable in the long run.

1.2 Objective of this document

This document is intended to serve as an **initial guide** for collecting user experience data from workshops and training sessions related to the resources developed by the FIN-CLARIAH consortium. It has been created both from data collected through semi-structured interviews¹ with potential end-users of DARIAH-FI (one of the two branches of FIN-CLARIAH, a Finnish research infrastructure for SSH) as well as information gathered via a selected narrative review on research design. Ultimately, however, the process for collecting user experience data from workshops and training sessions related to the resources developed by the FIN-CLARIAH consortium will depend on the institutions where the involved researchers are affiliated with, which may provide specific instructions, e.g., in terms of ethical reviews and software services. Therefore, this document should be read in conjunction with said stipulations.

2. Procedure for collecting data

2.1 Study design

Method. A first crucial step when it comes to collecting user experience data from workshops and training sessions related to the resources developed by the FIN-CLARIAH consortium is **determining the specific information you would like to gather**. For example, would you like to obtain large-scale measurable data about your resource? Then a more quantitative approach will work best for you. Would you like to obtain in-depth accounts of the experiences of end-users with your resource? Then maybe it would be best to apply a more qualitative approach. While this seems obvious, deciding between quantitative and qualitative approaches seems to

¹ A total of 34 semi-structured interviews (13 interviews with members of the DARIAH-FI development project and 21 interviews with non-members of the DARIAH-FI development project) were conducted between September 2022 and February 2023. Results from the first round of interviews are available at Sendra et al. (forthcoming).

also depend on the stage of the digital tools and materials in question (Figure 1). According to our data (Sendra et al., forthcoming), the consensus is to opt for a more qualitative approach during the early phases, and for a more quantitative approach in later stages.

Figure 1. Collecting user experience data according to the software development life cycle (SDLC). SDLC stages extracted from Shafiq et al. (2021).

Regardless of the methodology chosen, however, another point of agreement is that user experience data should be collected in multiple ways, meaning that both quantitative and qualitative approaches should be considered. For example, although during the later phases the consensus is to opt for a more quantitative approach, this does not mean that qualitative methodologies cannot be used occasionally to collect user experience data (and vice versa).

What to ask. A second crucial step when it comes to collecting user experience data from workshops and training sessions related to the resources developed by the FIN-CLARIAH consortium is **deciding which aspects of the user experience you would like to evaluate**. According to our data, the consensus is to ask about different aspects of the user experience. For example, it is equally important to assess the usability of the resources developed by the FIN-CLARIAH consortium as well as the quality of the documentation that accompanies them. However, not all aspects of the user experience can be evaluated in the same study nor the user experience itself can be assessed too frequently. Otherwise, providing comments regarding the user experience might take too long or represent a burden for the end-users, which eventually could discourage them from engaging in these type of studies.

Who to ask. A third crucial step when it comes to collecting user experience data from workshops and training sessions related to the resources developed by the FIN-CLARIAH consortium is **choosing who are the groups you are going to evaluate the user experience to**. This also involves thinking already during the design process about the user characteristics that

are relevant to improve the resources developed by the FIN-CLARIAH consortium. Obtaining user experience data can provide an understanding of who is using these resources, knowledge that could later be used, e.g., for better tailoring the educational resources offered by the facility. According to our data, the consensus is that user experience data should be collected from various end-user clusters. Our data also reveals that important user characteristics involve skill level and academic/professional background (Sendra et al., forthcoming).

2.2 Setup

Once the details regarding the method, what to ask and who to ask are sorted out, it is time to think about how to collect the user experience data. For example, the setup for collecting user experience data will not be the same if the workshop or training session to test the resources developed by the FIN-CLARIAH consortium happens online or face-to-face. According to our data, it is also important to consider that **collecting user experience data requires resources**, especially in terms of costs and personnel (Sendra et al., forthcoming). Therefore, it is necessary to assess which are the resources at your disposal to ensure the most optimal setup for collecting user experience data and not overreach. In other words, if there is only one researcher in charge of collecting user experience data during the workshop or training session, a qualitative approach such as a focus group might not be the most favorable setup.

<p>Is the workshop or training session going to happen online or face-to-face?</p> <p>How many people are going to take part of the user experience data collection process?</p> <p>If it is going to be online, what are my options? Do I have a subscription to a relevant service (e.g., Zoom)?</p> <p>If it is going to be face-to-face, what are my options? How is the room where the workshop or training session is going to happen?</p> <p>Do I need technical assistance? Do I need collaborators?</p> <p>Who is going to manage the user experience data collected? Are the necessary resources to address the problems raised within the data in place?</p>

Table 1. Examples of questions to consider before deciding the final setup.

Likewise, resources and their availability do not only refer to the user experience data collection process itself **but also to its subsequent implementation** (Sendra et al., forthcoming). That is, you can collect all the user experience data that you want, but if you do not have the resources to be able to manage that data and address the problems raised within it, the effort will have been profitlessly. According to our data, many of the teams in charge of the resources developed by the FIN-CLARIAH consortium have not considered collecting user experience data precisely for this reason. Another significant aspect, which is related to the question of balance raised in

the previous sub-section, is that you need to be able to determine the relevance of the user experience data collected (Sendra et al., forthcoming). That is, not all the problems raised might be that relevant, or not all the necessary resources to address them are at your disposal.

2.3 Data collection

After deciding on the study design and the setup for collecting user experience data, it is time to start the data collection process. However, this procedure starts way before the day the workshop or training session means to happen. The aspects to be covered regarding the data collection process can be divided in two areas, including participant recruitment and deployment. As for **participant recruitment**, the first thing to develop is an information sheet about the study to be distributed among your respondents. This also encompasses the potential preparation of consent forms and the possibility of undergoing an ethical review process, which will depend on which data are you going to collect and how you are going to collect it (e.g., in an anonymous way or not). The recommendation here is to check the guidelines of the institutions where the researchers involved in the study are affiliated with.

Once the necessary documents are ready, the participant recruitment process itself can start (e.g., through email). In this context, and regardless of what you do for collecting user experience data (e.g., surveys), respondents should always be informed about the study beforehand. As for **deployment**, it is important that the researchers involved in the study prepare themselves prior to the workshop or training session, especially if the collection of user experience data is going to happen within the workshop or training session itself. If there is more than one researcher involved in the study, also consider the arrangement of a preparation meeting before the workshop or training session, so that all people involved in the collection of user experience data are on the same page. Similarly, the day of the workshop or training session, it is advisable to review if all the necessary resources are prepared and ready.

3. Data management and other things to consider

In addition to all the steps mentioned in the previous section, the researchers involved in the collection of user experience data from workshops and training sessions related to the resources developed by the FIN-CLARIAH consortium will most likely need to develop a data management plan – especially if the idea is to collect large amounts of user experience data or during a long period of time. This document will help the researchers keep track of how to manage their data (e.g., in terms of storage, archiving, etc.). The necessity of creating a data management plan as well as which contents should include will depend once again on the guidelines of the institutions where the researchers involved in the study are affiliated with. Nevertheless, a good starting point for developing a data management plan is DMPTuuli (n.d.), resource created by the University of Helsinki and available both in Finnish and English.

Moreover, other aspects to consider when collecting user experience data from workshops and

training sessions related to the resources developed by the FIN-CLARIAH consortium is that the process should be simple, interactive and (if possible) integrated in the user interface of the solution. According to our data, **simplicity** and **integration** reduce potential burdens for the end-user, which might increase both the efficiency of the process and the number of responses collected. Similarly, our findings reveal that receiving a human response to feedback is highly valued among the end-users, which could be provided through **interactivity**. While it might be possible to not meet all these requirements (e.g., due to a lack of resources, time constraints, etc.), researchers involved in the collection of user experience data from workshops and training sessions should at least consider if they can satisfy them – either fully or partially.

Apart from collecting user experience data through the methods described in this document, another way of obtaining this type of information is through **log data**. The resources developed by the FIN-CLARIAH consortium, either digital tools or materials, leave a trace of records that are generated automatically and that have the potential to provide relevant information about the user experience (Rieh and Xie, 2006). For example, log data could reveal which functionalities are not being used, thus opening an avenue to improve or remove them. However, our results show that log data is something that is not usually considered, especially within people with non-technical backgrounds (Sendra et al., forthcoming). Moreover, although log data is seen as something that could provide more information about the user experience, a related issue is that obtaining and processing this type of information also requires resources (e.g., space).

4. Conclusion

As outlined in the beginning of this document, analyzing the user experience is an important step of the digitization of SSH. In terms of FIN-CLARIAH, finding out how end-users interact with the resources developed has the potential of providing relevant information that can later be used to guarantee the efficiency and sustainability of the research infrastructure. Nevertheless, collecting user experience data, either from workshops and training sessions or other activities, is not an easy task due to challenges such as a lack of resources and poor end-user engagement. Starting from our experiences of research infrastructure evidence-based development and with the support of relevant literature, this text provides a series of recommendations to consider when collecting user experience data from workshops and training sessions. Table 2 below outlines these suggestions in a summarized manner.

1. Define the objective of collecting user experience data and how you plan to achieve it
2. Consider the number of resources that are at your disposal and adapt your plan accordingly
3. Prepare both a recruitment and a data management plan and, if necessary, the relevant documentation in terms of research ethics (e.g., consent form)
4. Organize a preparation meeting before the collection of user experience data

5. If possible, collect user experience data in a simple, integrated, and interactive form

Table 2. Steps for collecting user experience data from workshops and training sessions.

5. References

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APPENDIX

Resources for creating a research protocol

According to the World Health Organization (WHO, n.d.), a research protocol should include the sections outlined in Table 3. It is possible that not all these sections are relevant for all studies, thus they should be assessed on an individual basis. Likewise, while the structure below might be more suitable for health-related studies (e.g., new drug application), the National Institutes of Health (NIH, n.d.) developed a research protocol template for behavioral and social sciences research involving humans. This specific template can be downloaded from NIH's website². The difference between a research protocol and an information sheet is that the former is addressed to a more scientific audience (e.g., ethics review committee) while the latter is intended for a more general audience, thus the language used should be less technical. However, the contents between the two documents might end up being quite similar.

PART 1	PART 2
Project summary General information Rationale & background information References Study goals and objectives Study design Methodology Safety considerations Follow-up Data management and statistical analysis Quality assurance Expected outcomes of the study Dissemination of results and publication policy Duration of the project Problems anticipated Project management Ethics Informed consent forms	Budget Other support for the project Collaboration with other scientists or research institutions Links to other projects CV of investigators Other research activities of the investigators Financing and insurance

Table 3. Recommended research protocol structure.

Source: WHO (n.d.).

² The template for behavioral and social sciences research involving humans can be downloaded from the following link: https://osp.od.nih.gov/wp-content/uploads/2019-03-28_BSSR_Protocol_Template.docx

Information sheet template

Below you can find an example of information sheet, in this case adapted for interviews. The following template is based on the information provided by Tampere University³.

[INSERT TITLE OF THE STUDY]

1. Introduction

You are invited to participate in...

After reading this document, you will have the opportunity to ask any questions you may have. Please take your time to carefully read this document. You will be requested separately to provide consent for participating in the study.

2. Purpose of the research

The purpose of this study is...

3. Description of the process

The study will be conducted... and will be based in...

We expect ... participants to take part in the study. Participants will/will not receive financial compensation for taking part in the study.

The study will be conducted in ... and will not take more than ... of your time.

4. Procedures for collecting research data

Data will be obtained from...

³ <https://www.tuni.fi/en/research/responsible-science-and-research/research-integrity/ethics-committee-of-the-tampere-region>

Any identifying information will be...

Data will be securely stored in...

5. Potential risks and benefits of participation

The procedures and methods used during this study do not involve any risks for you, either health, social, financial, or related to personal data breaches.

You will/will not receive any direct benefit from participating in the study. Data obtained is expected to...

6. Data confidentiality, processing, and storage

All personal data collected during the study will be processed in compliance with...

Any identifying information will be...

Data will be securely stored in...

7. Protecting the privacy of participants in research papers/publications

Data and materials related to the study will be retained by ... for ...

Data will only be made openly accessible...

8. Funding sources

The study is funded by...

9. Voluntary participation

Participation in this study is entirely voluntary, and you have the right to withdraw from the study...

Refusal to participate or discontinuing participation at any time will not have negative consequences for you.

Data collected to the point of withdrawal...

10. Privacy protection in the context of research papers and communicating about the study

Data will be confidential. No identifying information will be used in...

11. Use of data for non-research/later purposes

Data from the study will...

12. Inquiries

Please direct all inquiries about the study to...

13. Researchers' contact details

Name

Position

Affiliation

Phone number

Email address

Informed consent template

Below you can find an example of informed consent, in this case adapted for interviews. The following template is based on the information provided by Tampere University⁴.

[INSERT TITLE OF THE STUDY]

With this form, I declare that:

I have been requested to participate in the research study identified above. I have received information about the study in writing and have had the opportunity to ask questions from the researcher(s) conducting the study.

I understand that participating in the study is voluntary. I am aware that I have the right to refuse to participate and the right to withdraw from the study permanently or for a temporary period at any time and without giving a reason. I understand that any personal data collected in the course of the study will remain confidential.

I accept for the interview to be recorded.

I hereby give my voluntary consent for participation in this study.

Full name in block letters:

Place:

Date:

Phone number:

Email address:

⁴ <https://www.tuni.fi/en/research/responsible-science-and-research/research-integrity/ethics-committee-of-the-tampere-region>